

Jean Monnet Module
'DEBATING EUROPE'
INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL DYNAMICS OF
EUROPEAN INTEGRATION
(DEBUE)

Exploring High Impact Pedagogy

Curriculum and Guide

2022-2025

Civitas
! University

Co-funded by
the European Union

CONTENTS¹

DEBUE’S RATIONALE AND OBJECTIVES	3
Context and Significance	3
An Opportunity to Refresh EU Studies.....	4
An Opportunity for Self-reflection in Academic Practice during DEBUE	5
Challenges and Adaption	6
Aim of the Curriculum and Good Practice Guide	6
DEBUE’s Pedagogical Framework	6
High-impact Pedagogy	7
HIP Practical Checklist	10
DEBUE’s Theory of Change and Intervention Logic	10
ToC and Intervention Practical Checklist	11
DEBUE Teaching and Learning Matrix.....	12
Summary.....	13
TEACHING ELEMENTS	14
DEBUE Kick-Off Activities.....	14
Exercise: “How Do You Learn – and What Do You Know?”	14
Oxford Union Debates.....	16
How to Conduct Oxford Union–Style Debates – Step-by-Step.....	16
Checklist for Debates	21
Debate Assessment Grid.....	22
Scenario-building Exercises	23
Turning Point / Normative Approach to Scenario-building – EU in 2030	24
A Matrix Approach to Scenario-building and foresight for EU enlargement by 2030.....	27
Virtual European Classroom (VEC)	29
VEC - How to Do It?.....	30
DEBUE Visiting module on EU enlargement	31
Model Visiting Module: EU Enlargement – “From Neighbours to Members”	31
Writing Policy Briefs.....	33
The DEBUE Podcast Series: Co-Creating Europe in Sound.....	34
Purpose and Pedagogical Value	34
How the Podcasts Were Made: Step-by-Step Process	35
ANNEXES	37
ANNEXE 1. Kick-off activity	37
ANNEXE 2. Student feedback and reflection from DEBUE podcasts	38

¹ This publication was produced with the support of the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union under the Jean Monnet Module “Debating Europe: Internal and External Dynamics of European Integration” (DEBUE), grant number 101085339. The European Commission’s support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

DEBUE's Rationale and Objectives

The Jean Monnet module 'DEBUE' advances the study of European integration via a mix of teaching and training activities geared to the needs of BA and MA students from different disciplinary spheres and other stakeholders from a variety of countries.² The module was conceived at Collegium Civitas / Civitas University in 2021 / 2022 and builds on the nascent foundations in EU studies that were already in place. At its very core, **DEBUE was and remains concerned with stimulating and facilitating debate and reflection on EU and European issues in 'safe spaces' and on topics and concerns relevant to young people.** DEBUE is modelled on the following ideas: -

- **The incorporation of different types of stakeholders** in the delivery of activities, thus exposing students to policy and academic perspectives, civil society viewpoints and points of view emanating from both EU and non-EU states.
- **An international approach** that includes home and ERASMUS+ students, as well as foreign universities.
- **Interdisciplinarity across all its activities.** The module aimed to avoid disciplinary silos by encouraging students to bring political, economic, and social concepts and knowledge into their analysis and presentation work.
- **High impact pedagogy** geared to maximising gains in student learning, engagement, and retention,
- **Reflective learning** embedded across all learning activities, with students encouraged to define topics for debates and podcasts as co-creators and subsequently to reflect on their learning performance and achievements.
- **An integrated approach** combining different ways of learning and teaching beyond normal classroom conditions.
- **Creative assessments** that are job-relevant and test multiple skills and competencies, as well as knowledge.
- **An emphasis on policy relevance** particularly to do with European integration in its internal and external dimensions.
- **Sustainability and gender** as mainstreamed factors throughout all activities.

Building on these foundational elements DEBUE implemented BA and MA teaching modules 'Debating Europe'; Virtual European Classrooms; a DEBUE visiting teaching at Tbilisi State University on EU enlargement, Podcasts on European Issues; Scenario Building exercises and policy briefs.

Context and Significance

DEBUE was not conceived in isolation. The importance of debating and engaging with EU issues, especially amongst young people has been emphasised in multiple studies concerned with democracy and civic participation.³

² Initially created in 2022, this manual was updated in 2024 and again in 2025. It is also in use in academic year 2025/26.

³ European Youth Forum. (2022). Safeguarding civic space for young people in Europe. Brussels: European Youth Forum. Available at: <https://www.youthforum.org/files/220428-PP-civic-space.pdf> Council of Europe. (2025). Our Voices: Misinformation and Debate in a Pluralistic World (Study Session). Strasbourg, 5–10 May 2025. Available at: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/youth/-/our-voices-misinformation-and-debate-in-a-pluralistic-world>

EU Youth Dialogue. (2025). EU Youth Conference Report, Lublin 2025: Disinformation and participation. Available at: https://www.frse.org.pl/brepo/panel_repo_files/2025/06/27/ugmsvs/euyd11-eu-youth-conference-report-lublin-eu-pl-pre.pdf

Tsouparopoulou, E., et al. (2025). European Youth and Digital Engagement: Attitudes, Skills, and Participation. Journal of Youth Studies. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43151-025-00168-z>

European Democracy Youth Network & European Partnership for Democracy. (2023). Youth Participation Handbook: Volume 1. Available at: https://edyn.eu/storage/2023/03/YDC_Handbook.pdf

Within this literature there is a broad consensus that debating is more vital than ever. **Open and informed debate has the potential for strengthening citizens' capacities to critically evaluate competing narratives, distinguish fact from propaganda, and engage meaningfully with the European project.** DEBUE's experience shows that for young people structured debate in university settings created a fresh **space for dialogue**, enabling them to test arguments, challenge biases, and develop media literacy. Crucially, in a context where disinformation campaigns efficiently erode trust in democratic institutions and the EU's legitimacy, promoting debate on EU topics fosters resilience and pluralism. **Debate also helps bridge the gap between citizens and EU institutions by transforming abstract policies into relatable issues that shape everyday life.**

DEBUE's aims and objectives also echoed the goals of the **2022–2023 Conference on the Future of Europe**, which sought to make the Union more participatory, responsive, and in turn, resilient. The Conference put a strong emphasis on inclusive dialogue particularly with young people about democracy, rule of law, and human rights as underpinnings of Europe's future. Several of DEBUE's activities align directly with the recommendations of the conference.

An Opportunity to Refresh EU Studies

The field of European and EU Studies needs refreshing primarily because over the past decade the European Union itself has fundamentally changed, moving from an integration-focused project to one facing multiple simultaneous crises and profound internal and external pressures. **The impulses for renewal stem from three sources: geopolitical realities, internal challenges, and also the need for pedagogical relevance.** Accordingly, DEBUE emphasises the following features and themes within all of its activities as basic parameters

Figure 1. Thought Parameters for DEBUE Teaching and Learning

- **The Age of Crisis and Conflict:** The EU is no longer defined solely by treaties but by its response to external shocks, the weaponisation of energy, and the rise of global competition. The discipline must shift to analysing the EU as a geopolitical actor.
- **Contested Borders and Enlargement:** The discipline needs to fully integrate the Eastern Partnership states and the Western Balkans. As DEBUE highlights, the political and social dynamics in countries such as Georgia, Ukraine, and Moldova—and their struggle with democratic norms—are now central to the EU's identity and future.
- **Authoritarianism and Backsliding:** The field must move beyond simply studying "European values" to actively analyzing and combating **democratic backsliding** both within EU member states and in candidate countries, as seen also in gender-related challenges
- **Policy Complexity:** New strategic pillars—the **Green Deal** and the **Digital Decade**—require a multidisciplinary approach that goes beyond Political Science and Law. European Studies must integrate knowledge from environmental science, data ethics, and technology policy to remain relevant.
- **Identity and Fragmentation:** The rise of populism, Euroscepticism, and nationalist movements suggest that a unified European identity is fractured and should not be taken for granted.
- **Transnational Challenges:** Contemporary issues such as migration, climate change, and pandemic preparedness are inherently transnational. Therefore, EU studies' curriculum should prioritise the study of the EU's capacity for coordinated crisis response and its role in global governance.

Refreshing EU and European studies also entails a reflection on theory and its utility. The challenge to EU integration theory is one of empirical relevance and explanatory power in an evolving and often volatile European political landscape. Students taking part in DEBUE are encouraged to evaluate

existing theories and to question if they have reached their limitations and perhaps defunct in the face of challenges and trends in the 21st century. **From a students' perspective, traditional theories are often unrelatable because they struggle to connect with real-world problems of the day.**

Crucially, the inability of core theories to explain current themes and challenges in Europe, including the battle over core values might leave a critical gap in students' understandings, since theories often seem extraneous to real-world developments and happenings. With this observation in mind, DEBUE's **curriculum moved decisively away from only learning about theories and institutions towards active engagement through structured debating, defending analysis, and critically challenging opposing viewpoints.**

An Opportunity for Self-reflection in Academic Practice during DEBUE

In the field of **European / EU Studies**, reflecting on what kind of educator one is arguably essential. Teaching about Europe today means engaging with diversity, contested values, and shifting geopolitical realities within increasingly international classrooms. **Academics are called to move beyond delivering information to fostering the intercultural awareness, critical thinking, and democratic dispositions that allow students to understand and question Europe's evolving role in the world.** In an age of misinformation, polarisation, and global uncertainty, reflective teaching helps scholars stay attuned to the lived experiences of their students, many of whom, in the case of DEBUE, come from EU candidates, neighbouring states or even further afield. This ensures that European Studies remains not only intellectually rigorous but also socially relevant, to cultivate a generation of learners capable of dialogue, empathy, and informed engagement with the idea of Europe.

This reflective stance lies at the heart of **DEBUE's philosophy**. The project was founded on the belief **that transformative European Studies teaching depends as much on *how we teach* as on *what we teach*.** DEBUE encourages academics to become conscious designers of learning experiences and to consider how their assumptions, methods, and interactions shape students' understanding of Europe. By reflecting on their own pedagogical choices, educators contribute not only to improved classroom practice but also to the broader transformation of European higher education into a more participatory and values-driven space.

To do this effectively, academics should begin with themselves and by examining their own teaching values, approaches, and assumptions. This reflection can transform teaching from routine practices into a deliberate act of academic citizenship. Just as we might encourage students to reflect on *how* they learn, academics and teachers benefit from reflecting on *how* they teach — and *why*. The following prompts help to clarify teaching identity, values, and impact:

Purpose: What kind of learning do I most want to inspire — analytical rigour, civic engagement, creativity, inclusion?

Approach: Do I see myself as a facilitator, mentor, or transmitter of knowledge? How do I balance guidance with autonomy in the classroom?

Engagement: When are my students most energised and alert: during discussion, reflection, application, or experimentation?

Design: How do my teaching methods reflect my own beliefs about learning and knowledge?

Impact: What lasting change do I hope to create in my students and how do I know when it's happening or not?

Growth: What evidence, feedback, or peer dialogue can help me develop as an academic?

Challenges and Adaption

From both an academic and operational perspective DEBUE brings immense opportunities but also challenges associated with international academic cooperation. Whilst partnerships and new forms of cooperation and joint activities might seem sound at the start of a project, changes in personnel, academic programmes and student numbers affect implementation and the scope of a project. This implies a need for flexibility and adaptability. **From DEBUE's perspective a flexible approach was adopted by conducting ongoing searches for partners and collaborators within Higher Education, but also from the Think Tank and education sectors.** This adaptability and openness had pragmatic goals but was also valuable since it extended the reach and impact of DEBUE's activities to a broader set of beneficiaries and stakeholders than originally forecast. This also included opportunities to interact with other Jean Monnet funded projects.

Like other EU-related activities DEBUE has also been affected by transformations occurring beyond its control. The DEBUE approach was to 'embrace' change. Since its inception geopolitical changes in the Eastern neighbourhood have seen the return of full-blown war in Europe, and the re-ignition of the enlargement dynamic. After DEBUE was conceived, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine became EU candidates which affected some of the initial underpinnings of the project. Such profound changes in the EU landscape meant that **DEBUE's curriculum and focal points had to be adjusted to assure relevance and to garner the interest of students, whilst keeping true to its overall objectives.** This goal is particularly salient in the context of working with international groups of students from outside the EU, including those from EU candidate states. In essence, the DEBUE experience is that Jean Monnet teaching modules are likely to benefit, in terms of relevance and impact if activities adapt to developments occurring on the ground.

Finally, the field of learning and teaching in higher education is awash with new methodologies and exciting ideas, yet **the main challenge is often to do with how to operationalise new methods and approaches in a context when time and resources are in short supply,** planning horizons are limited and university authorities have their own cycles for designing and implementing new courses. In other words, there is sometimes a tension between the desire for innovation implied in a Jean Monnet teaching module and institutional realities which potentially impede change.

Aim of the Curriculum and Good Practice Guide

The purpose of this guide is threefold (i) to share experiences and best practices in EU integration studies derived from the DEBUE Jean Monnet module. (ii) to provide a detailed overview of the activities undertaken during DEBUE's implementation in the form of a practical "how-to" guide (iii) to reflect on some of the pedagogical lessons learned from implementing DEBUE.

The document is intended for students and academic staff engaged in EU integration studies, offering both methodological insight and inspiration for teaching and learning activities. The guide covers all aspects of DEBUE including its pedagogical framework and core teaching and assessment activities.

DEBUE's Pedagogical Framework

At the outset of DEBUE's implementation, a key question guided the design process: "What kind of module do we want this to be?" The Jean Monnet grant offered not only an opportunity to deliver new content, but also to innovate in teaching methods, build fresh institutional capacities, and explore new directions in European Studies education. DEBUE was conceived to achieve all these aims.

To translate this vision into practice, an overarching methodological approach and conceptual framework were established to support DEBUE's pedagogical design and implementation. This framework integrates four interrelated dimensions: -

- **A focus on high-impact pedagogy**, ensuring that learning activities are engaging, participatory, and transformative for both students and staff.
- **A theory of change**, capturing how DEBUE's learning processes contribute to wider goals such as strengthening European citizenship, democratic resilience, and intercultural understanding.
- **A clearly articulated intervention logic**, linking inputs, activities, and outputs to concrete outcomes and long-term impact in line with Jean Monnet objectives.
- **A learning and teaching matrix** to translate the project's conceptual and methodological design into practical teaching practice.

This four-part integrated framework ensured that DEBUE's teaching is not only innovative but also purposeful and evidence based. It aligns classroom activities with the broader objectives of Jean Monnet actions: to deepen understanding of the European Union, foster critical thinking about its role in the world, and equip future graduates with the skills and values essential for Europe's democratic and intercultural future.

High-impact Pedagogy

High-impact pedagogy (HIP) denotes teaching and learning practices that have a strong and lasting influence on students' understanding, engagement, and personal development. These approaches aim to move beyond traditional knowledge transmission to create active, reflective, and participatory learning environments that promote deep learning, intercultural competence, and civic responsibility and awareness. DEBUE sought to further this approach.

Since the early 2000s, research in higher-education pedagogy has shown that student engagement and transformative learning are maximised when teaching is participatory, relational, and inquiry-driven. Scholars such as **Kuh** and **Fink** highlighted how high-impact practices, such as debate, collaborative projects, experiential learning, and problem-based inquiry generate long-term gains in student motivation, retention, and transferable skills. More recent studies have expanded this by emphasising new digital and intercultural dimensions and demonstrating that impact is greatest and sustainable when students are treated as **partners and co-creators** in learning processes.⁴

The European Commission's European Strategy for Universities (2022) explicitly endorses these ideas, describing high-impact pedagogy as learner-centred, inclusive, transdisciplinary, and closely

⁴ Bond, M., Bedenlier, S., Marín, V. I., & Hammond, T. (2020). *Breaking down barriers: High-impact practices for online and blended learning*. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(6), 3215–3233. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09844-z> Bond, M., & Bedenlier, S. (2022). *High-impact learning in the postdigital university*. *Postdigital Science and Education*, 4(3), 879–897. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-022-00333-1> Bovill, C. (2020). *Co-creation in learning and teaching: The case for students as partners*. *Higher Education*, 79(6), 1023–1037. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-019-00453-w> Felten, P., & Lund, A. (2021). *Relationship-rich education: How human connections drive success in college*. Johns Hopkins University Press. Fink, L. D. (2013). *Creating significant learning experiences: An integrated approach to designing college courses* (2nd ed.). Jossey-Bass. Healey, M., & Healey, R. L. (2019). *Students as partners in learning and teaching in higher education: The impact of partnership*. *Teaching & Learning Inquiry*, 7(2), 18–29. <https://doi.org/10.20343/teachlearningqu.7.2.2> Kuh, G. D. (2008). *High-impact educational practices: What they are, who has access to them, and why they matter*. American Association of Colleges and Universities (AAC&U). Umbach, P. D., & Wawrzynski, M. R. (2019). *Faculty do matter: Active learning and student engagement revisited*. *Research in Higher Education*, 60(2), 141–160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11162-018-9519-9>

connected to societal needs. This orientation aligns directly with the objectives of Jean Monnet actions and DEBUE, which encourage innovation and students as co-creators.

Kamil Zwolski’s 2025 publication on teaching about EU power, provides interesting food for thought with regards to integrated learning as a high impact pedagogy (HIP) method in the field of European studies.⁵ For Zwolski, the multi-level governance structure of the EU, which is characterised by policy-making involving national, regional, and supranational actors means that the use of HIP tools including simulations and Problem-Based Learning (PBL), are ideal for replicating the EU’s multi-actor / multi-level polity, allowing students to experience negotiation and compromise firsthand. He also advocates an approach in EU studies which is professionally relevant by giving assessments that balance an academic essay with a practical policy document, which mirrors the skills demanded in the ‘real world’. Zwolski’s overall point is that by fostering both deep theoretical understanding and essential real-world skills through a blended and practice-focused design, best practice for preparing students for careers in European affairs can be achieved.

Figure 2 Core Principles of High-Impact Pedagogy in DEBUE

Engagement	&	Participation
Learning is powerful when students are actively involved as co-creators of knowledge. Structured debates, student-led seminars, and peer-review sessions encourage dialogue and ownership of learning.		
Experiential	&	Inquiry-Based Learning
Students learn through doing, experimentation, and reflection on real-world challenges. Scenario-building exercises and simulations allow students to explore EU decision-making, negotiation, and policy processes.		
Intercultural	&	Collaborative Learning
Diverse perspectives and teamwork develop empathy, openness, and European identity. The Virtual European Classroom connects students from different countries to collaborate on shared EU topics.		
Digital	&	Innovative Practice
Technology enhances access, creativity, and communication. Podcast production and blended-learning formats integrate media, research, and dissemination.		
Reflection	&	Feedback
Reflection transforms experience into understanding and supports lifelong learning. Students produce short reflective statements and self-evaluations after debates or projects.		

⁵ Zwolski, K. (2025). Teaching European power: the case for an integrated approach. *European Politics and Society*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23745118.2025.2500580>

Civic	&	Democratic	Relevance
High-impact pedagogy links academic content with societal values and citizenship. Debating EU enlargement and values fosters civic awareness, democratic resilience, and critical engagement.			

Within **DEBUE**, **HIP is both a guiding principle and a practical methodology**. The module combines a range of interactive and reflective approaches: - debate, scenario-building, and project-based learning to stimulate independent thinking and collaboration. The Virtual European Classroom and teaching at Tbilisi University extend these experiences into a transnational space, while podcast production and policy-brief writing foster creativity, communication skills, and engagement with real-world issues. Collectively, these methods transform abstract knowledge into lived experience, allowing students to test ideas, develop argumentation skills, and cultivate a sense of European citizenship.

HIP in **DEBUE** also seeks to enhance employability and promote social inclusion by ensuring that students from diverse disciplinary and national backgrounds can contribute equally to shared projects. Ultimately, DEBUE's approach demonstrates that high-impact pedagogy is not only about *what* students learn but *how* they learn. DEBUE contributes to a model of European higher education that is transformative, inclusive, and resilient—preparing graduates to think critically, act responsibly, and participate confidently in Europe's democratic future.

Figure 3 shows DEBUE's three-layered model for creating transformative learning experiences. The *Engage* or *Experience Layer* immerses students in active, participatory tasks that simulate real-world decision-making. The *Interpret* or *Reflection Layer* deepens understanding by prompting learners to analyse outcomes, discuss implications, and connect experiences to theory and concepts. Finally, the *Act* or *Application Layer* extends learning beyond the classroom, as students apply insights through creative and policy-oriented outputs such as podcasts, briefs, or collaborative presentations. Together, these layers build a cycle of experience, reflection, and action that supports deep and high-impact learning geared to DEBUE's goals.

Figure 3. Designing for High Impact

Layer	Purpose	Example in DEBUE
Engage (Experience Layer)	Immerse students in authentic tasks that demand participation and decision-making.	Oxford-style debates; scenario-building; virtual european classrooms; kick-off activities.
Interpret (Reflection Layer)	Encourage learners to analyse what happened and why it matters.	Peer discussion; post-debate / scenario debriefs. Feedback.
Act (Application Layer)	Translate learning into new contexts or tangible outputs.	Student podcasts, policy briefs, scenario papers, collaborative online presentations.

HIP Practical Checklist

The following quick diagnostic tool is used in DEBUE - If at least five boxes are ticked, the session likely qualifies as high-impact.

- Do students talk more than the lecturer?
- Does the activity connect directly to a real-world European issue?
- Are collaboration and peer learning built in?
- Is structured reflection included after the activity and beyond the classroom?
- Is feedback comprehensive and continuous rather than end-loaded?
- Are diverse voices explicitly encouraged and respected?
- Does the activity challenge students intellectually and ethically also?
- Does the activity integrate digital or cross-campus collaboration tools effectively?
- Are students encouraged to link their learning to professional or civic contexts beyond the classroom?
- Is there space for students to co-design or adapt parts of the activity?
- Does the activity include an element of formative self-assessment or peer review and reflection?

DEBUE's Theory of Change and Intervention Logic

Integrating a Theory of Change (ToC) and intervention logic into a teaching module provides a transparent, structured framework that links teaching practice to learning outcomes and broader goals in a succinct way. It enables educators to make explicit how particular activities such as debates, simulations, or problem-based projects are intended to produce specific shifts in student knowledge, skills, and also attitudes. This approach not only clarifies the *why* behind pedagogical design but also strengthens accountability, reflection, and evidence-based improvement. For academics, using a ToC promotes curriculum coherence, supports the scholarship of teaching and learning, and provides a foundation for evaluating impact on democratic, analytical, and civic competences. These methods also make it easier to share and discuss best practices with colleagues.

Developing a Theory of Change typically begins with defining the ultimate impact the module seeks to achieve, such as fostering critical thinking or active citizenship and then working backward to identify the intermediate outcomes, outputs, activities, and inputs that will make this happen. The intervention logic complements this by mapping causal links and assumptions underlying these steps.

In the case of DEBUE, the ToC helps demonstrate how experiential learning methods translate into meaningful educational and democratic outcomes. It provides a coherent rationale showing that **DEBUE is not only a teaching innovation but a structured intervention aimed at strengthening democratic culture and European citizenship through higher education.**

The *DEBUE* Jean Monnet module operates on the premise that **debate and experiential learning can transform how young people understand and engage with the European Union.** Thus, DEBUE's theory of change and intervention logic are rooted in the notion that *knowledge acquisition*, when combined with *dialogue, reflection, and participation*, produces active, informed, and resilient citizens. The theory of change is thus: -

DEBUE is founded on the principle and assumption that students learn about the European Union most effectively when they are active participants in inquiry, dialogue, and problem-solving. > By combining Oxford-style debates, scenario-building, the Virtual European Classroom, and student-led podcasts, DEBUE transforms traditional EU teaching into an interactive, practice-oriented experience. > These activities stimulate analytical thinking, intercultural communication, and civic engagement, enabling students to connect theory with lived realities. > Through this multi-method approach, participants build both academic and democratic competences—reflecting critically, engaging collaboratively, and applying knowledge to authentic European challenges. > In the longer term, DEBUE contributes to strengthening democratic culture, enhancing the quality and appeal of EU studies, and empowering young Europeans, particularly from candidate and Eastern Partnership states to become informed, reflective, and participatory citizens.

Figure 4. DEBUE’s Intervention Logic

ToC and Intervention Practical Checklist

1. Define Purpose and Scope

- Clarify the overarching aim of the teaching module (e.g., deepen EU understanding, foster civic engagement).
- Identify the intended audience and level (undergraduate, postgraduate).
- Specify whether your ToC is for design, evaluation, or research purposes—or all three.

2. Establish Desired Impact

- Define the long-term change you aim to achieve (e.g., critical, participatory, intercultural competences).
- Link this to institutional or societal goals (democratic learning, inclusive education).

3. Identify Outcomes and Outputs

- List the short- and medium-term outcomes expected from student learning (skills, behaviours, attitudes).
- Specify tangible outputs (debates, policy briefs, podcasts, collaborative projects).
- Ensure each outcome logically leads toward the stated impact.

4. Map Activities and Inputs

- Identify the learning activities that drive change (lectures, discussions, fieldwork, online collaboration).
- Specify inputs required—time, digital tools, partnerships, or staff expertise.
- Align each activity with one or more intended outcomes.

5. Make Assumptions Explicit

- Note the assumptions linking each stage.
- Identify potential barriers or risks.

6. Visualise the Logic

- Create a simple diagram or table showing *Inputs* → *Activities* → *Outputs* → *Outcomes* → *Impact*.

7. Validate and Refine

- Share the draft ToC with colleagues, students, or evaluators for feedback.
- Test it during module delivery: - does practice reflect the intended logic?
- Revise to reflect new insights, evidence, and student feedback.

DEBUE Teaching and Learning Matrix

DEBUE’s Learning and Teaching Matrix serves as a practical instrument for coordinating, monitoring, and reflecting on teaching and learning activities. **It helps ensure that each component is clearly connected to defined learning outcomes and broader Jean Monnet objectives.** By visualising the relationship between pedagogy, delivery, and desired impacts, the matrix provides a transparent overview of how DEBUE’s innovative, student-centred methods translate its theory of change and intervention logic into classroom practice. For students, the matrix provides orientation and clarity. It helps them understand the why behind each learning activity, illustrating how participation in a debate, simulation, or podcast is connected to broader learning goals and assessment criteria.

Figure 5. Teaching and Learning Matrix for DEBUE

Method Category	Teaching and Learning Tools / Activities	Purpose and Application in DEBUE	Intended Learning Outcomes (Knowledge, Skills, and Values)
Student-centred and experiential methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oxford Union Debates • Project-based learning and policy briefs • Scenario-building exercises 	Engage students in analysing complex EU policy and integration challenges through applied and participatory tasks. Link theory to real-world contexts, including governance, security, and enlargement scenarios.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deep understanding of EU, policy-making, and global challenges. • Analytical, negotiation, and teamwork skills. • Practical problem-solving and adaptability. • Enhanced employability, leadership, and citizenship
Technology-enhanced and resource-based methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blended learning (combining in-person and online teaching) • Technology-enhanced sessions (interviews, simulations, podcasts) • Students use of open resources (EU databases, digital archives) for research • Virtual European Classroom 	Integrate traditional and digital instruction to encourage flexibility, innovation, and collaboration between students from different countries and institutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened digital literacy and online collaboration skills. • Intercultural competence and networking experience. • Improved ability to conduct digital research using EU resources. • Greater awareness of transnational perspectives in EU studies.

Traditional and hybrid methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive lectures • Flipped classroom • Hybrid approaches (on-site and online) • Differentiated instruction forms 	Combine foundational lectures with active learning and discussion, adapting to diverse student needs and institutional contexts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solid conceptual grounding in EU integration and European values. • Critical reflection and comparative analysis. • Inclusive learning environment • Broader understanding of EU citizenship and participation.
Output- and communication-focused methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy briefs • Podcast series • Debates 	Link academic study with real-world communication and outreach. Strengthen students' ability to express ideas clearly and engage different audiences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong written and oral communication skills. • Ability to translate academic analysis into public and policy discourse. • Greater civic awareness and media literacy. • Confidence in participating in democratic and policy debates.
Research- and inquiry-based methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent and group research projects • Guided empirical studies using EU reports, surveys, and policy documents • Integration of findings into classroom debate and written outputs 	Develop a research mindset through critical inquiry and exposure to professional analytical practices. Encourage use of open-access EU data and policy sources.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence in research design and data analysis. • Deeper understanding of EU governance and policy processes. • Strengthened employability through transferable analytical and project-management skills. • Reinforcement of democratic, evidence-based, and intercultural thinking.

Summary

DEBUE's pedagogical framework has four cornerstones: a **Theory of Change**, **Intervention Logic**, **High-Impact Pedagogy (HIP)**, and a **Teaching and Learning Matrix**. It assumes that students learn about Europe most effectively through *doing*, especially by debating, analysing, and reflecting. The Theory of Change maps the pathway from awareness to active citizenship, while the Intervention Logic links activities to outcomes. HIP ensures that debates and reflection generate lasting learning. The Teaching Matrix aligns knowledge, skills, and values with transparent assessment of students themselves. **Without such a framework, EU studies risk reverting to passive, information-heavy teaching that limits student engagement, critical thinking, and ultimately their civic awareness.**

Teaching Elements

The following sections describe all of DEBUE's teaching activities and offer a step-by-step illustration of how they can be replicated in the context of EU / European Studies. The text is ordered as follows

1. DEBUE Kick-Off Activities
2. Oxford Union Debating
3. Scenario-building Exercises
4. Virtual European Classroom
5. DEBUE teaching module at Tbilisi State University on EU Enlargement
6. Policy briefs
7. Podcasts

DEBUE Kick-Off Activities

Kick-off activities provide an opportunity to encourage students to be reflective learners, develop social skills in the classroom and for professors to ascertain levels of knowledge on a given subject amongst the student cohort. Such activities are also useful in online settings to break down barriers and to nurture discussion and dialogue 'between screens'.

Exercise: "How Do You Learn – and What Do You Know?"

This opening-semester exercise helps students understand their individual learning styles and study preferences, reflect on how to build an effective personal learning methodology and assess their initial knowledge of the European Union and European integration.

By completing this activity, students will: Identify their dominant learning style(s) and techniques. Create a short personal learning methodology statement. Gain awareness of their starting level of knowledge about the EU. Set goals for both skill and content development throughout the course.

Part 1 – Kick-off Quiz: How Much Do You Know About the EU? (10–15 minutes)

Purpose: To warm up, stimulate curiosity, and give the professor a diagnostic snapshot of students' familiarity with European integration.

Instructions:

Students complete the quiz individually (on paper or Kahoot). Afterwards the professor reviews answers to spark discussion.

Sample Questions:

- How many member states are currently in the European Union?
- Which institution proposes new EU legislation?
- What is the difference between the *European Council* and the *Council of the EU*?
- Which countries are currently recognised as EU candidate states?
- What does the term *Copenhagen Criteria* refer to?
- Which EU treaty introduced the concept of European citizenship?
- Name one major policy area managed primarily at the EU level.
- True or False: The European Parliament can dismiss the European Commission.

- Which country most recently joined the EU?
- (Open) What does “European integration” mean to you, personally?

Discussion:

Review a few key answers, correct misconceptions, and highlight themes that will appear in the course. Encourage students to note areas they’d like to learn more about.

Part 2 – Learning Style Self-Assessment (15 minutes)

Put the following questions to the students and ask them to write their answers.

When I’m learning something new, I prefer to...

- a) Watch or visualise it b) Read about it c) Discuss it d) Try it out

When I prepare for exams or essays, I usually...

- a) Create mind maps b) Highlight and summarise texts c) Work in groups d) Rehearse or apply concepts

I remember information best when I...

- a) See images b) Hear explanations c) Write or talk it through d) Do something with it

Then, appraise responses → identify main preferences amongst the group: **Visual, Auditory, Reading/Writing**, or a mixture.

Part 3 – Reflection & Discussion (10 minutes)

In pairs or small groups, students discuss: What did you learn about your learning style? Were you surprised? What methods seem to help you most when studying for complex topics like EU integration? How might you adapt your strategies this semester and further into the future?

Part 4 – Personal Learning Methodology Statement (15–20 minutes)

Each student writes a short (circa. 200 words) reflection that includes:

- Their main learning strengths and challenges.
- Study techniques that work best for them (e.g., diagrammes, summaries, group debate, podcasts).
- How they will use these techniques to build EU knowledge throughout the course.
- One personal learning goal for the semester.

Oxford Union Debates

Oxford Union-style debating modules provide BA and MA students at Collegium Civitas and other universities with a unique opportunity to directly benefit from high impact pedagogy envisaged in DEBUE.

*“DEBUE demonstrates that debate is not just a useful pedagogical tool, but that it is also a **democratic safeguard by helping participants to strengthen their knowledge and skills to discriminate between fake news and verifiable facts**” (DEBUE academic partner, Lithuania, July 2024)*

The Oxford Union debate format is a **respected tradition of structured argumentation in higher education** and is highly participatory. Originating at the University of Oxford in the nineteenth century, it has since been adopted worldwide as a model for critical thinking, dialogue, and civic engagement.⁶ On the basis of DEBUE’s experience: -

Debating provides a **counterbalance to passive, lecture-based learning**. While traditional teaching often emphasises the absorption of information, debate requires students to **apply, question, and defend ideas** in real time. It nurtures analytical thinking, evidence-based reasoning, and active listening—skills central to democratic citizenship and academic inquiry. In contrast to the one-way flow of lectures, debating transforms students from recipients of knowledge into **co-creators of understanding**, sharpening confidence and intellectual independence in profound ways.

Jean Monnet DEBUE debates covered a range of topics relevant to European integration, values, social and security policies, Europe’s role in the world and identity issues. **One of the most attractive aspects of Oxford Union debates is that almost any topic can be selected and transformed into a valid and interesting motion, therefore classes tend to be inclusive and popular**. Debates in classes are also a good way of integrating students from different disciplines and countries, since everyone is starting at a comparable level.

As mentioned earlier, debating in classes reinforces essential competences for European citizenship: namely the ability to listen, reason, persuade, and disagree respectfully. **By requiring participants to defend a position, which is sometimes contrary to their own beliefs, the format nurtures empathy, adaptability, and intellectual discipline**. Debates are also highly appreciated by students.

‘Joining in a DEBUE debate gave us the space to disagree respectfully and learn from one another. The debate helped me see that democracy in Europe is about dialogue and not only institutions and voting’ (Student, Collegium Civitas, October 2024)

How to Conduct Oxford Union–Style Debates – Step-by-Step

Choosing the Motion – two class sessions are needed

The **motion** defines the debate and actually determines its success. A strong motion should be clearly phrased, balanced, relevant, and sufficiently controversial and even provocative to encourage deep analysis and discord. Motions are always expressed as a proposition beginning with *“This House believes that...”* or *“This House would...”*

⁶ The Oxford Union <https://oxford-union.org/>

During DEBUE we found our motions by brainstorming during one or two class sessions to establish what topics interest people. A list of broad themes and topics was then created, which the students voted on. Once the broad topics were selected our job was to formulate a motion. In previous years the following motions were selected.

- This house believes that Turkey has no place in the European Union.
- This house believes that international sports events should not be held in countries with poor human rights records.
- This house believes that strong dictatorships are better than weak democracies.
- This house believes that gender equality is achievable.
- This house believes that the war in Ukraine cannot be won.
- This House believes that the EU should prioritise the rule of law over economic interests.
- This House believes that European democracy is best protected by a stronger European Parliament.
- This House would suspend enlargement until internal EU reform is complete.
- This House believes that the EU should offer membership to Ukraine by 2030.
- This House believes that the European Green Deal demands too much from smaller member states.
- This House would introduce a universal EU carbon tax.
- This House believes that AI threatens democracy.
- This House believes that gender parity should be mandatory in European political institutions.
- This House believes that citizenship education should be compulsory in all schools.

When thinking about your motion keep in mind relevance and educational value; select topics linked to learning outcomes and course themes. **In EU studies, this could include enlargement, migration, digitalisation, climate policy, or gender equality.** The motion should allow students to apply theory to contemporary European challenges. Also, motions framed around hypothetical or current moral dilemmas often provoke rich debates.

Figure 6. Debating Tips

What Makes a Good Oxford Union Debate/Speech	What Makes a Bad Oxford Union Debate/Speech
Rhetoric and Style: The audience is persuaded by rhetoric. A good speech incorporates a stylish delivery, charisma, strong humour, and memorable anecdotes alongside logical arguments.	Pure Logic Without Style: Relying only on dry, technical, or purely factual arguments without using wit, storytelling, or rhetorical flair to connect with the audience.
Audience Engagement (Points of Information): Accepting a few Points of Information (POIs) offered by audience members to show confidence, address counterpoints in real-time, and make the debate interactive and lively.	Poor Engagement or Flow: Taking too many POIs, which breaks the flow of your speech, or taking none at all, which makes you appear unwilling to defend your arguments.
Rebuttal and Timing: Effectively listening and responding directly to the key arguments made by the opposing team. Keeping strictly within the allotted time limit is highly valued by the audience and Chairman.	Ignoring Opponents: Delivering a pre-prepared speech that completely ignores the opposing team's main arguments, or continuing to speak after the time limit is called.
Respecting Forms of the House: Adhering to the formal rules, addressing the Chairman correctly	Offensive or Insensitive Remarks: Using jokes or language that is offensive, inflammatory, or crosses accepted boundaries of taste (even if ad-

("Mr/Madam Chairman"), and maintaining decorum and courteous behavior.	libbed), which can quickly cost the speaker all support.
Strong, Structured Argument: Presenting a clear, cohesive case with well-developed points that directly support the motion (Proposition) or directly refute it (Opposition).	Failing to Fulfil the Role: Not addressing the core motion, making a speech that is irrelevant to the topic, or failing to introduce your team (for the First Proposition speaker).

Compiling the team and explaining the rules – one class session is needed.

Five people are involved in each debate (the rest of the class, plus invited people are the audience – who later vote after hearing the debate), the chair and four speakers (two FOR the motion and TWO against).

Chairperson: Controls the debate and is neutral (if there is a draw, then the Chair gets a casting vote). They give a 4–5-minute basic introduction saying why the motion is important and then tell the room the rules of the debate and introduce the speakers. Students should volunteer for the role they wish to have and be comfortable with the motion and their position in it. This being said, it is important to tell students that they do not have to necessarily personally agree or disagree with the motion, in fact a debate can be an interesting opportunity to ‘try out’ a different perspective and to see an argument from the ‘other side’.

Doing the research – between five and ten hours are needed.

Successful debating depends on rigorous research, guided by both independent work and structured academic support. Students should begin by analysing the motion carefully, identifying key terms, assumptions, and points of contention. It is normal for students to need regular reminders of the motion wording and which side (proposition or opposition) they represent, as this helps keep research coherent and arguments relevant. Research should draw on credible academic, policy, and media sources, such as journal articles, official EU or UN documents, think-tank analyses, and reputable news outlets. Each team member should gather evidence for their side and anticipate counter-arguments from the opposing team.

To ensure progress and quality, weekly catch-up meetings should be held with the facilitator or tutor. These sessions allow teams to discuss emerging findings, clarify misunderstandings, and receive guidance on structure, tone, and use of evidence. They also help students begin compiling and rehearsing their speeches gradually, rather than leaving preparation until the end.

Effective debate preparation is therefore a collaborative and iterative process, combining individual research initiative with continuous mentoring and peer discussion. The ultimate goal is to transform research into a logical, persuasive narrative that connects evidence to the motion, reflects analytical depth, and showcases confident, informed argumentation.

Teams should rehearse transitions, timing, and responses to potential questions. Preparation builds confidence and also ensures fluency.

Promoting your debate and getting audience

DEBUE used debates to promote the Jean Monnet module and to invite a good-sized audience to watch the live debate and to vote. Posters were designed and social media used to promote and draw awareness to the event. Students designed posters and disseminated them via Facebook, Instagram, the university’s website etc.

Civitas University Co-funded by the European Union

CIVITAS UNIVERSITY DEBATE

"Immigration is good for Europe"

This event is part of a Jean Monnet Module 'DEBUE; (Debating Europe - Internal and External Perspectives)

Thursday, April 24
2025

Meet the Debate Officials

The event will follow the Oxford Union Debate format, consisting of two teams, who will rotate depending on the topic.

Jean Monnet Professor Kerry Longhurst
Host and Lecturer at Civitas University

Hicran Akşit
Chair from Turkey

Sultonmurodov Nodirbek
Introducer from Uzbekistan

24 April, 2025
17:30 - 19:00
MICROSOFT TEAMS
hicraanaksit@gmail.com

Uniwersytet Civitas Co-funded by the European Union

DEBATING EUROPE

Internal and External Dimensions of European Integration
DEBUE Jean Monnet Policy Workshop
12 June 18.00-20.00 Online

SPEAKERS

Ventura Tabuada Ana
Sarihan Eda
Akşit Hicran
Davydik Mary
Casinos Lanchazo Lucia
Marabuto Gabrielle
Kampka Justyna
Bohdana Dyrenko
Pham Diep Anh
Sultonmurodov Nodirbek

UNDER

Dr. Kerry Longhurst

Figure 7. DEBUE posters for Oxford Union Debates

How to proceed in a debate – allow two hours for a single debate

The Chair opens the debate, welcomes people and then reads the motion. They introduce the topic and gives a 5-minute basic and enthusiastic introduction saying why the motion is important and then tells the room the rules of the debate. Introduces the speakers by name and remind everyone of the timing. Then, the speakers Begin in the following order: -

- First Speaker for the motion (8 MINS)
- First Speaker against the motion (8 MINS)
- Second Speaker for the motion (8 MINS)
- Second Speaker against the motion (8 MINS)

Throughout the debate the Chair must make sure the time allotted is not exceeded and that the audience stays quiet and respectful.

Then after all speeches the Chair opens the debate to the floor (rest of the class / audience).

This can last up to 20 minutes.

After the open debate has finished the Chair asks one person from each side to summarise their arguments in two minutes maximum. The Chair then reads the motion (to make sure they understand it.)

The Chair asks:

- I. Those for the motion to put up their hands (writes down the number).
- II. Those against the motion to put up their hands (writes down the number).
- III. Chair then says whether the motion is carried (proposer win) or defeated (opposer win) by saying "I declare this motion – reads motion – carried or defeated."

Tips for the Chair person

The Chairperson is essential to the professionalism, pace and fairness of the debate.

- **Neutrality:** Maintain impartiality and avoid personal commentary.
- **Timekeeping:** Adhere strictly to allocated speaking times.
- **Inclusivity:** Encourage participation from quieter students.
- **Civility:** Intervene if discourse becomes disrespectful.
- **Summary:** Conclude by thanking participants and conducting a fair vote.

The Chair models the norms of democratic discussion and ensures that the debate remains a safe space for learning.

Adapting the Format for Online or Multilingual Contexts

Oxford-style debates can be effectively conducted in virtual and mixed-language classrooms. Use breakout rooms for team preparation. Employ digital polls (e.g., Mentimeter, Zoom polls) for the House vote. Encourage bilingual summaries where participants express key points in two languages. Record sessions (with consent) for reflection and feedback. DEBUE debates were particularly appreciated by visiting ERASMUS+ students.

'Taking part as a speaker in a debate at Collegium Civitas was a highlight of my ERASMUS experience in Poland. As well as improving my confidence in English I learnt a lot about EU issues and identities.'
Erasmus+ student at Collegium Civitas from Spain 2024-2025.

Checklist for Debates

Before the debate

- Select a clear, balanced motion framed as "This House believes that..."
- Ensure the motion aligns with course learning outcomes (critical thinking, EU understanding, argumentation skills).
- Assign or confirm teams (Proposition / Opposition), balancing ability and engagement.
- Clarify roles
- Distribute or post the assessment grid and student checklist in advance.
- Set and communicate time limits
- Brief students on rules of decorum, turn-taking, and respectful conduct.
- Prepare the room setup – clear seating for teams, central moderator position, visible timer.
- Ensure technology (microphones, projector, timer, slides) functions smoothly.
- Optionally appoint a student chair or timekeeper to support facilitation.

During the debate

- Start on time and briefly introduce the format and rules to all participants.
- Maintain neutrality and encourage equal participation across teams.
- Monitor time strictly; give subtle signals when speakers are near the end.
- Observe argument structure, delivery, and teamwork for grading.
- Encourage audience engagement (questions, voting, or reflections).
- Intervene only when necessary (off-topic, disrespectful, or excessively long contributions).
- Take structured notes aligned with the five grading criteria:

After the debate:-

- Complete the assessment grid for each speaker or team.
- Provide constructive oral or written feedback, highlighting specific examples.
- Discuss what constituted effective argumentation and evidence use.
- Encourage brief student reflection on what they learned about persuasion and critical thinking.
- Optionally summarise the debate's main insights or implications in a short debrief or class note.
- Reflect as facilitator: what worked well, what could be improved next time?
- Use the debate as a formative assessment opportunity and as part of the Virtual European Classroom exchanges, when applicable.

Debate Assessment Grid

This grid provides a transparent, fair and detailed framework for evaluating student debate performance. It combines qualitative and quantitative dimensions across five equally weighted criteria. Each criterion is marked out of 20 points (total 100). The final score is then converted into a grade on the 5+ to 2 scale.

Figure 8. Debate Assessment Grid

Criterion	Weight	5+ Outstanding	5 Very Good	4 Good	3 Pass	2 Fail
Content & Knowledge	20%	Deep, well-researched understanding; integrates evidence, theory, and nuance.	Strong and accurate knowledge with solid use of evidence.	Sound grasp of main issues but lacking depth or precision.	Basic factual knowledge; limited or inaccurate evidence.	Lacks understanding; factual errors or irrelevant material.
Structure & Argumentation	20%	Logical, compelling, and strategic argumentation; clear narrative arc.	Well-structured arguments; mostly logical and persuasive.	Reasonably coherent but uneven or repetitive.	Weak structure; unclear argument or focus.	Disorganised; no coherent argument.
Rebuttal & Engagement	20%	Excellent engagement with opponents; sharp, respectful rebuttals.	Responds effectively to most opposing points.	Some engagement but limited spontaneity or follow-up.	Minimal response to counterarguments.	No engagement; ignores opposing side.
Delivery & Communication	20%	Confident, dynamic, and articulate delivery; maintains audience attention.	Clear and professional delivery with minor lapses.	Understandable but hesitant or uneven tone.	Monotone, unclear, or overly scripted.	Inaudible, disorganised, or inappropriate style.
Teamwork & Coordination	20%	Seamless collaboration; roles clearly defined and complementary.	Good balance between speakers; minor coordination issues.	Some teamwork evident but inconsistent.	Uneven participation; little cohesion.	No teamwork; members unprepared or absent.

Each criterion is marked out of 20 points, giving a total score out of 100. The final grade is determined according to the following: -

Final Score Range	Grade	Descriptor
90–100	5+	Outstanding / Excellent
80–89	5	Very Good
70–79	4	Good
60–69	3	Pass
Below 60	2	Fail

Scenario-building Exercises

Scenario-building is a ‘forward-looking’, participatory teaching method that encourages students to explore how complex EU / european policy issues might evolve in uncertain or unpredictable futures.

Scenario building exercises are a critical tool for navigating the complexity and uncertainty of the modern world, especially in domains such as international relations, which seem at present to be on a knife-edge of unpredictability. These exercises move students to actively confront multiple, dramatically different futures, from cooperation to fragmentation and beyond. DEBUE included scenario building exercises into classes on European issues and international relations. The activity provided students with a novel opportunity to engage in a highly participatory learning experience, which also nurtured teamwork and cross-cultural communication.

‘The scenario building exercises that we did in class were an exciting way to explore and discuss the future role of Europe in the world – what might happen and what would need to be done to avoid negative trends and mitigate the effects of unknown or emerging domestic and external challenges and threats’ Collegium Civitas student from Ukraine, March 2025.

Within the DEBUE Jean Monnet module, scenario-building is one of the programme’s high-impact learning methods. It complements debating by shifting the focus from analysing the past and the current, to the future. The method cultivates strategic foresight, systems thinking, intercultural understanding, as well as policy understanding at EU and national levels. Scenario-building also responds to the pedagogical priorities emphasised in EU higher-education policy; namely, to strengthen transversal skills such as collaboration, digital competence, and critical reflection. It aligns with DEBUE’s theory of change, which posits that students learn best when they engage actively, co-create knowledge, and relate abstract EU concepts to real-world contexts.

Rather than predicting ‘the’ future, scenario exercises help students think in pluralistic terms. Through this process, learners become more aware of how narratives and choices shape and influence Europe’s / EU trajectories and thus gain confidence to engage in debates. **In so doing, DEBUE strives to turn students from bystanders to stakeholders.**

A ‘try it and see’ approach was taken at the beginning. DEBUE used multiple methods for scenario building, which were tailored to the size of the class, their interests and capacities. DEBUE opted for approaches suitable for BA and MA students with limited knowledge of European integration. The following provides an overview of what ‘worked best’ for DEBUE. The preferred model was a turning point or normative approach, which is described below for an EU 2030 exercise. A matrix-based approach was also used for a shorter and narrower scenario-building exercise on EU enlargement 2030.

Turning Point / Normative Approach to Scenario-building – EU in 2030

This is good for a semester-long module as it gives sufficient time for deep research, co-creating the scenario and for presenting and discussing findings and results. It also allows for explaining the rules and expectations at every juncture, to keep everyone on board.

The following is a plan for a **scenario-building exercise about the EU in 2030**. The method presented below is a *turning point* or *normative* approach, which builds scenarios around a pivotal challenge or decision that may alter the EU's trajectory.

STEP ONE: - The professor drafts a short scenario brief to emphasise that we are at a turning point. This framing prompts students to start their path on forward-looking analysis and helps students start to imagine the pressures, events and opportunities Europe might face. **TIP Emphasise the creative nature of the exercise (allow 2 - 4 hours of class time, plus homework).**

The brief: - Since the 1950s, European integration has advanced through crises as much as through visionary leadership. Every turning point — from the oil shocks and the Cold War's end to the eurozone crisis, migration pressures, and the pandemic has tested, but also arguably strengthened, the Union's capacity to adapt. What began as a post-WW2 economic community of six has evolved into a Union of twenty-seven, wielding a single market, a common currency, and global ambitions.

The 2020s have plunged the EU into an age of volatility. Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine has redrawn the continent's security map and forced an unprecedented energy pivot, which many EU states have found hard to adapt to. The rush to end dependence on Russian hydrocarbons has accelerated investment in renewables and critical raw materials but also revealed deep structural vulnerabilities: volatile energy markets, fragile supply chains, and uneven political will to sustain the green transition. Climate change has become a defining driver of policy, linking energy, security, food, migration, and competitiveness in a web of interdependence.

Yet the Union's internal cohesion is under intense strain. In several member and candidate states, oligarchic networks and captured media sectors continue to shape politics and economies, eroding accountability. Democratic backsliding and selective compliance with EU norms; most visibly in Hungary but echoed elsewhere have exposed the limits of Brussels' leverage. The principle of shared values, once the EU's unique moral compass, is now contested within its own borders. Misogyny, anti-gender campaigns, and identity-based populism have moved from the margins to the mainstream, threatening hard-won equality gains, corroding trust in liberal institutions and embedding polarisation.

Meanwhile, the global environment is shifting at pace. China's global interests and stealthy rise, the U.S. under Trump, and Russia's irredentism have undermined the contours of the old liberal order. New alliances in the Global South are redefining the terms of multilateralism, for example via BRICS or the Shanghai Cooperation Council. Inside Europe, debates about strategic autonomy and enlargement to Ukraine, Moldova, and the Western Balkans clash with concerns about overstretch and internal fragmentation. In amongst this situation, discussions about a new form of enlargement have emerged.

By 2030, the European project could take radically different forms. One future might see a confident geopolitical Union leading the world's green transformation, defending democracy, and speaking with one voice. Another envisions a splintered Europe: an inner core of integration surrounded by 'semi-detached' states, where nationalism, inequality, and democratic fatigue start to erode solidarity and once-common values.

STEP TWO: - Divide into three teams of four to six students. Each team should represent a different **paradigm** – best, worst and ‘wildcard’ scenario.

- **Team one** - Best-case – What would a highly positive European outcome look like? Which choices make it possible? What needs to occur for this to come about?
- **Team two** - Worst-case – What might failure or regression mean? What would need to happen / not happen for this to come about?
- **Team three** - Wild-card – What unexpected disruption could change everything – a technological breakthrough, geopolitical shock, social movement, environmental incident?

This stage is not about prediction but about defining meaning. Debating what 'best' and 'worst' actually signify encourages ethical reflection. Whilst wild-cards force creativity by introducing low-probability yet still conceivable, high-impact events. **TIP Explain clearly what these paradigms mean, using terms such as *desirable*, *undesirable*, or *disruptive*. TIP if using teams create sub-teams for each groups, so that they can meet ad hoc and store relevant files and documents. (allow 5 hours of class time).**

STEP THREE: - Students research and identify ‘drivers’. They should begin the research process by identifying major drivers of change that influence the topic. These will be political, social, demographic, technological, economic, environmental, or legal. It is important that drivers are not seen in terms of isolated silos, but rather dynamically and interactive. Reliable and verifiable data based on primary and good-quality secondary academic and policy sources should be used. DEBUE found that data on ESPAS, World Bank, UN, ILO, IOM, IMF, and EU websites were useful for gathering baseline information and to verify trends and developments. Students need to distinguish between predictable / ongoing trends and major uncertainties. Teams should maintain shared research folders and meet weekly with the facilitator to review progress, check sources, and refine arguments. **(allow 4 hours of class time, plus 6 - 8 hours of homework – with professor being on-call to respond to questions and to monitor progress). Homework tasks also work very well online. TIP To guide students in STEP THREE lecturers should get students to ponder:**

- What are the key trends that are almost certain to continue?
- What trends have become less dynamic or irrelevant?
- What uncertainties or flashpoints could dramatically change outcomes?
- Are the sources that you are relying on credible and balanced, have you verified the facts?

STEP FOUR: - Students retreat into their paradigm groups and start to work out together their main drivers and also what it means to be best, worst and wildcard and then report back to the professor with their common views. **TIP Have students grasped what 'best' and 'worst' mean for different types of stakeholders? Check that the wild-card group is imaginative yet also plausible. (Allow 3 hours of classroom time).**

STEP FIVE – Students continue to work in their paradigm groups. Alongside their research, the teams write two to three pages describing its future scenario as a draft. Narratives should outline key events, actor responses, and implications and outcomes. Papers can include visuals, graphs, short timelines, or maps. Weekly facilitator check-ins help refine your storyline, improve logic, and ensure balanced participation. **TIP Professor should meet with each team to check on progress (Allow 2 hours of classroom time, plus 4 -5 hours of homework time).**

STEP SIX - Teams present their scenarios in 15-20 minutes, using visuals or slides to illustrate key features. Following each presentation, questions about plausibility, logic, and evidence are put to the teams. Teams should respond constructively and note feedback for revision. **TIP Check that students**

explain in sufficient details their assumptions. Invite other students, external academics and practitioners to the presentations to get fresh perspectives and challengers (Allow 2 – 3 hours of classroom time).

STEP SEVEN – Teams go away and refine their papers in light of their presentations and feedback and then submit their papers – aiming at 5 - 6 pages (Allow 3 – 4 hours of homework time).

STEP EIGHT – Final class debrief and feedback, lessons learned and links to ‘real’ debates. Identify what factors most shaped the scenarios and what policy actions could steer towards better outcomes. **TIP** Get students to think about what assumptions influenced the team’s scenario. What uncertainties had the greatest impact on the outcomes? What actions could policymakers take today to shape desirable futures according to the exercise? (Allow 1 – 2 hours of classroom time).

DECEMBER 18, 2024

Co-funded by the European Union

COLLEGIUM CIVITAS

PRESENTATION

Europe and the World 2035

Over the past months, our students have used research and forecasting methodologies to build informed, credible, and plausible scenarios for the future of Europe.

On Wednesday, they will present their interim results according to:

- Best case scenario
- Worst case scenario
- Wild card scenarios

Join Us for the Presentation

17 Wednesday, 18 December

📍 Online at 3 PM CET

This activity is part of the EU-funded 'Debating Europe: Internal and External Dimensions of European Integration' module (DEBUE Jean Monnet Module 2022-2025) at Collegium Civitas, Warsaw.

Key Focus Areas

- **Triggers and Trends:** Emerging trends and systemic factors likely to shape change in the next decade.
- **Global Events:** How natural disasters, conflict, and migration amplify global insecurities as 'threat multipliers.'
- **'Black Swan' Scenarios:** Unexpected developments that may shift the world order and international relations.

Figure 9. Poster for online scenario-building exercise presentations

A Matrix Approach to Scenario-building and foresight for EU enlargement by 2030

The matrix approach to scenario building is useful as it gives students focus and clarity, especially in the early stages of learning about the EU. By limiting analysis to two critical drivers, this approach means that students only have to engage with the most impactful variables relevant to the subject matter, rather than a wide range, or even exponential, set of variables. This results in four scenarios that are plausible, distinct and internally coherent. DEBUE used a matrix approach for a shorter EU enlargement focused exercise.

INITIAL STEP: - This approach assumes that students might not have a great deal of EU insight, therefore reading should be prescribed before the exercise begins and introductory lectures given also. **(allow 3 hours of class time and 2 hours of homework).**

STEP ONE: - Design the matrix, with students as co-creators. Select two high-impact uncertainties to form the axes of a 2x2 matrix. Subsequently, the four squares create four distinct ‘futures’. **(allow 1 hour of class time and 3 hours of homework reading on EU enlargement – primary and secondary sources).**

STEP TWO: - Divide into four teams of four to six students. Clarify responsibilities and roles early on so that each member contributes research, analysis, and creative input **(allow 1 hours of class time).**

STEP THREE: - Introduce the Matrix and make sure that everyone understands it. Carefully explain what the axis mean; - *Vertical*: EU Political Cohesion (High vs. Low). High cohesion in practice means fast

unanimous decision-making and agreement on core values. Whereas low means states are likely to use vetoes, coalitions of the willing emerge and potential policy paralysis emerges. *Horizontal*: The pace of reforms in EU candidate states (Fast vs. Slow). Especially the essential areas of the *EU Acquis*: - rule of law, anti-corruption, economic competitiveness, democratic institutions etc. **(allow 1 hour of classroom time).**

STEP FOUR: - Define the four squares, go over the four predetermined scenarios to explain how the combination of the two variables leads to the outcomes and resulted assumed in the matrix. For example, why fast reforms twinned low cohesion equals selective integration. Then ascertain the current situation by asking students to identify the current reality on the matrix and to explain their answers and viewpoints, ask:

- Is EU cohesion presently high or low? Give examples of this.
- Is the pace of EU reforms in candidate states rather fast or slow, and why, are there differences between the states?
- Can you identify some external factors or 'drivers' that could push the situation into a different quadrant (square) on the matrix? For example; (cohesion): US election, the outcome of the war in Ukraine, internal EU economic crisis; (for reforms: A successful undemocratic coup / fast backsliding in a candidate country, a major EU financial aid package, a fixed deadline for accession, relaxing of EU enlargement criteria.

(Allow 2 hours of classroom time and possibly 1 hour of homework).

STEP FIVE (part one): - Time to get into the details, to develop nuance and identify pathways for each scenario. Assign one of the four quadrants (squares) to each group. At this stage, teams move towards 'creative synthesis' by transforming their assigned quadrant into a plausible, evidence-based narrative of the EU enlargement process. The job is not to predict but to imagine credible futures based on logic, data, and policy insights, demonstrating evidence of reading and research. The following process is followed: -

- Teams start by defining a common baseline namely where is Europe positioned today along the two axes EU political cohesion and the pace of candidate reforms? What concrete developments define this current reality: the war in Ukraine, Hungary's veto politics, the green transition, enlargement fatigue, or new geopolitical alignments (amongst many others)? This baseline anchors the scenario and importantly prevents unstructured speculation and drift away from logic.
- Next, students should list five to seven critical drivers shaping EU enlargement towards the year 2030. These must include political, economic, social, environmental, and technological factors. In doing this, it is important to classify them into: - predetermined or strong existing trends that are likely to persist, such as digitalisation, climate urgency, demographic decline, and critical uncertainties the outcomes of which could shift the future. Here could be regime change in an EU candidate country, EU constitutional reform, an environmental catastrophe, or a major wave of migration wave.
- In their teams the students then discuss how these forces interact and which combinations might push/pull their scenario toward the quadrant's logic: - 'United and Expanding, Selective Integration, Fragmented Europe, or Frozen Enlargement.

(allow 3 hours classroom time in break out groups, plus 1-2 hours of homework).

STEP FIVE (part two): - Students should build a timeline from 2025 through to 2030 by mapping five to six 'turning points' that connect the 'present' to the envisioned 2030. Each milestone should be

able to answer: Who acts? (EU institutions, member states, candidate governments, other external powers); What changes? (policies, institutions, alliances, social dynamics) What comes next? (effects on cohesion, reform pace and stages, and legitimacy of EU enlargement processes) This step links 'structure to agency', which should ensure that futures emerge through political choices and not 'abstract trends'.

(allow 2 hours classroom time in break out groups, plus 1-2 hours of group homework).

STEP SIX: - Time to write up the narrative by producing a 2000-word scenario paper following this type of structure: -

1. Short overview to describe what Europe looks like in 2030. Has enlargement advanced, stalled, or split? What is the general political and social climate in Europe?
2. Talk about drivers and triggers to identify your 5–6 key forces that shape this future.
3. Provide a chronology of 2025 through to 2030. In other words, tell the story of how Europe moved from today to 2030. What events / decisions caused change to occur? Use milestones where appropriate.
4. Mention the winners, losers, and implications to ascertain who gains and who loses in this scenario? Include what happens to democracy, gender equality, or oligarchic influences? How might all of this shape the EU's credibility and values?
5. List some signs that this scenario might already be emerging, ie. changes in EU cohesion, reform progress in candidate states, or public opinion and societal views on enlargement.
6. Mention takeaways by finishing with 2–3 short recommendations: what should EU leaders or candidate governments do to hopefully move towards best outcomes and avoid the worst?

(allow 3-4 hours of homework time).

STEP SEVEN: - Groups presents their 10-minute narrative. Other participants ask questions, followed by a group discussion about which scenario is the most desirable, which is the most disruptive (high impact, high uncertainty?) and which scenario is the most plausible based on current trends? Finally, ask the students to assume the role of European Commission President and answer the following question; *knowing these four potential futures, what core policy recommendation would you make today to avoid the worst-case scenarios and accelerate towards the best one?* **(Allow 2-3 hours of classroom time).**

Virtual European Classroom (VEC)

The Virtual European Classroom (VEC) is one of the flagship innovations of DEBUE. VEC created a live, transnational learning environment in which students and educators from multiple institutions, including universities, think tanks, and high schools worked together online to discuss some of the key challenges and debates to do with contemporary Europe, including values and identity, enlargement, security, geopolitics and gender. VEC became a valuable pedagogical experiment and potentially a community of practice, showing how European Studies can be interactive, inclusive, and directly relevant to peoples' everyday lives.

At its core, VEC transforms learning from passive knowledge acquisition into active, informed and research-based engagement. Using Zoom as a low-barrier digital platform, each VEC session connected three or more institutions in real time around a common pre-agreed theme. As far as possible, each participating team produces a short discussion paper (up to 1500 words), which is presented by one or two students during the online session. The structure mirrors an academic conference: a short keynote at the beginning, aimed at being accessible and relatable, which highlights the main themes

and sets an inclusive tone for participants of all academic levels. Student presentations follow, each accompanied by a Q&A and general discussion.

To bolster coherence and variety, each VEC is organised into clusters of thematic focus. Teams select which cluster they wish to write and present on, enabling participants to pursue their interests while maintaining balance across the overall event. During one VEC thematic clusters included:

- European Security
- EU Enlargement
- Rule of Law and Democracy
- Feminist Foreign Policies

For another VEC, emphasis was placed on the future of Europe / scenarios, European citizenship, youth and identity.

Editions of the Virtual European Classroom were successfully organised with overseas collaborators. The first, was developed with the Institute for European Studies at Tbilisi State University (Georgia) and the European Humanities University (Lithuania), was held under the title “Perspectives on the EU’s Role in the Eastern Neighbourhood: Security, Democracy, and the Rule of Law.” Students investigated questions such as the EU’s changing role as a security provider after the war in Ukraine, the merits of an independent European defence posture, and the value-based versus interest-based logic of the Union’s external action. The second VEC expanded the concept by including Warsaw-based high schools, alongside the Romanian EU Institute and Bucharest University. This also involved ‘Europe Direct’ in Poland and Romania. It offered a bridge between secondary and tertiary education and introduced younger students to structured academic debate and provided early exposure to university level learning about the EU. Teachers were actively involved in guiding the process, helping students refine arguments, moderate discussions, and connect classroom learning to real-world issues relevant to youth. This made the exercise instructive for educators as well as for students, since it enabled a novel exchange of teaching practices and demonstrated how debate-based learning can be integrated across educational levels and transnationally.

‘For our high school students, the Virtual European Classroom was a welcome opportunity to engage with university-level discussions about the EU in a welcoming space. It made complex ideas about Europe’s values and enlargement tangible and gave our pupils the confidence to express their opinions among peers from other countries’. Lyceum Teacher, Warsaw, July 2025).

Across both editions, VEC brought together participants from ten countries, including Poland, Georgia, Romania, Lithuania, Armenia, Ukraine, Belarus, Moldova, Italy, and Spain. The sessions showed that international academic cooperation can flourish without physical mobility, relying rather on creativity, and shared purpose. In terms of educational benefits and rationale, VEC also reflects DEBUE’s overall theory of change, in as far as it involves the gaining of research skills, facilitates ‘real-time’ knowledge synthesis and self-appraisal, provides a forum for cross-cultural communication and fosters collaboration between students and teachers / professors, as well as with Think Tankers and civil society.

VEC - How to Do It?

Based on the DEBUE experience, VEC is a very flexible and scalable format that is adaptable to other Jean Monnet modules, EU studies courses, or cognate international partnerships. Successful implementation depends on coordination and alignment across all partners.

1. Identify partners from different EU or neighbouring states, including universities, think tanks, and schools with overlapping interests.
2. Agree on a common theme that fits the academic priorities of all partners.
3. Structure the event into clusters, giving teams the autonomy to choose their topic.
4. Ensure curricular alignment. When working with university partners, it is good to make sure that VEC complements each institution's existing curriculum and does not distract students from their main studies. Early planning among faculty helps keep the workload realistic and the activity academically integrated and viewed as 'added-value'.
5. Set clear preparation guidelines for papers, time allocation, and presentations. Tell participants how much time they are likely to need to prepare.
6. Host the event on Zoom (3–4 hours in total), beginning with a concise keynote designed to be accessible and relatable for all participants – this is important for creating a safe space.
7. Facilitate inclusive dialogue, ensuring equal speaking time and mutual respect for everyone, but especially school-age participants.
8. Recognise participation. Issuing certificates of participation is recommended, as it provides a motivational and professional reward for students while highlighting institutional cooperation.

'DEBUE is international education in action. By engaging students from across Europe in values-based debate, it turns EU integration into a shared learning experience. Universities in the Eastern Partnership region can particularly benefit from DEBUE's example, which shows how dialogue fosters understanding of EU norms.' University Professor, Romania (June 2024)

DEBUE Visiting module on EU enlargement

Model Visiting Module: EU Enlargement – "From Neighbours to Members"

Partner: Institute for European Studies, Tbilisi State University
Instructor: Dr Kerry Longhurst, Collegium Civitas (Jean Monnet Grant Holder)

This visiting module was developed and delivered under the **DEBUE Jean Monnet Module** to strengthen cooperation between Collegium Civitas (Poland) and **Tbilisi State University (TSU), Georgia**. It demonstrates how DEBUE's **high-impact, participatory pedagogy** can be applied in a partner-university context to enhance learning about EU integration and enlargement.

The course complements TSU's own Jean Monnet initiative. Together, these modules contribute to a growing regional network of Jean Monnet teaching focused on **EU enlargement, democracy, and reform in the Eastern Partnership**. Around 25 students from TSU benefitted from the classes.

Delivered in October 2025, the module combines intensive classroom sessions with guided discussions, applied readings, and a short-written assessment.

Overview

'From Neighbours to Members – Impulses and Consequences of EU Enlargement' examines the historical evolution, political economy, and future trajectories of EU enlargement processes. This two-day, ten-hour module (5 ECTS) uses interactive lectures and structured debate to explore both **policy mechanics and normative implications** of enlargement.

Learning Objectives

By the end of the module students will be able to: Explain the **motivations, logic, and outcomes** of successive EU enlargement rounds. Analyse the **current enlargement dynamic** following Russia's invasion of Ukraine. Assess the performance of candidate states against the **Copenhagen Criteria** and cluster methodology. Evaluate the **Eastern Partnership** as a preparatory framework for membership. Reflect on the **geopolitical, democratic, and societal dimensions** of enlargement.

Schedule Summary

Day / Hours	Themes & Key Questions	Teaching Mode / Core Reading
Day 1 (hrs 1–2)	Why enlarge? Historical logics and lessons from 2004–2013.	Lecture + discussion. Piedrafita & Torreblanca (2005); Green Cowles & Smith (2000).
hrs 3–4	Current drivers and challenges; moral and strategic arguments.	Lecture + discussion. Sorgi (2023); Scicluna & Auer (2023); Orenstein (2023).
hr 5	The Eastern Partnership: rationale, achievements, and limits.	Lecture + discussion. EaP CSF Index (2023).
Day 2 (hrs 6–8)	Assessing Ukraine, Moldova, and Georgia: progress and obstacles.	Seminar. EaP Index and Longhurst (2023).
hrs 9–10	The future of enlargement: costs of non-enlargement, staged accession, and EU reform.	Round-table debate. Carnegie (2024); The Conversation (2024); CEPS (2023).

Assessment: Final Paper (3000 words)

Choose one question and produce an evidence-based essay. Indicate in a footnote whether any AI tools were used. **Grading:** *Mid-term element (40 points):* literature review, conceptual framing, and methodology. *Final exam (60 points):* argumentation, analysis, and evidence.

Essay Questions

1. What were the political and economic consequences of the 2004 and 2007 enlargements for (a) new member states (b) the EU.
2. State capture and corruption remain the greatest barriers to accession. Discuss.
3. What are the pros and cons of a **fast-track enlargement** for Ukraine and Moldova.
4. With reference to one candidate, evaluate whether the **Copenhagen Criteria** remain a valid benchmark.
5. What have been the most significant achievements and limits of the **Eastern Partnership**.
6. Is enlargement still the EU's most effective **foreign-policy tool** and example of **transformative power**?

Pedagogical Features (DEBUE Alignment) - Combines **interactive lectures, guided discussion, and analytical reading**. Encourages **inter-university collaboration** and intercultural learning between EU and Eastern Partnership students. Connects theory, data, and lived experience to improve **policy literacy and employability**.

Lessons learned - The module confirmed the **value of short, intensive, dialogue-based formats** in promoting engagement and comparative insight. Students from Georgia and neighbouring countries

demonstrated strong awareness of the normative appeal of EU membership but also expressed growing realism about political and institutional obstacles.

Writing Policy Briefs

The policy brief became one of DEBUE's most valuable assessment methods, reflecting the module's emphasis on connecting analytical and academic rigour with professional and employment relevance. Within DEBUE, policy briefs were used in the Debating Europe class and in other International Relations and EU Studies courses, where they proved to be effective in developing policy literacy, and persuasive communication in particular. Unlike a standard academic essay, a policy brief is a professional document designed to inform decision-makers. It is therefore concise and evidence-based. It asks students to translate complex issues into clear and actionable recommendations, thereby prompting them to think and communicate as if they were policy professionals. The exercise reflects DEBUE's high-impact pedagogy.

METHOD: - Students are asked to imagine that they are **policy advisers** working for a Foreign Minister, an EU Commissioner, or another senior official who requires a short, credible, and timely briefing. Their task is to help her/him understand a current issue, its implications, and to hear about possible responses. The brief has to be written in a professional and analytical tone, since it is aimed at a busy person who expects clarity, timeliness and precision over theoretical background.

Briefs should identify **what has happened and why it matters, analyse the causes, effects, and likely developments, outline policy options and 'trade-offs', and finish with specific, realistic recommendations.** The focus should be on a recent or an ongoing issue, ideally from the previous few weeks, that is relevant to the EU / Europe.

The recommended length is around 1,500–1,700 words (excluding annexes and references). Students are expected to use **primary sources such as official EU documents, press releases, verified statements, and data sets.**

The policy brief follows a structure that promotes logic and balance:

1. **Title** concise and non-academic (e.g. *EU–Moldova Relations: Managing Expectations after the 2025 election*).
2. **Executive Summary** (250 words) written last, but placed first, to summarise the issue, key findings, and recommendations.
3. **Description of the Issue** what happened, when, and why it matters.
4. **Causes and Context** background factors and trends.
5. **Key Actors** who is involved, who decides, and who is affected.
6. **Significance and Consequences** the wider implications for the EU or national interests.
7. **Recommendations** three to five concrete, evidence-based, and time-bound proposals.
8. **Sources** list all official and primary materials used.

Students are encouraged to be concise and purposeful and to use short sentences and clear logic. Sub-headings and bullet points can help in this regard, as can simple visuals such as tables or charts to illustrate trends (cite sources and dates). Recommendations should be actionable. Students should always be reminded not to use secondary and / or outdated sources or provide 'generic' advice such

as ‘enhance cooperation’ or ‘develop a policy on.....’ Successful briefs are persuasive, sharply focused, and rooted in verified data and evidence.

The policy-brief exercise furthers DEBUE’s approach to learning through practice. It asks students to synthesise information quickly, assess competing arguments and lines of discord, and to develop credible solutions. Furthermore, It cultivates such higher-order skills, such as critical thinking, data interpretation, structured communication, and audience / target awareness. For instructors and professors , this assignment provides a simple yet transformative way to combine research, teaching, and employability outcomes. DEBUE’s experience highlights several key lessons for successful implementation.

- The task should be framed early in the semester, with examples of good briefs provided to clarify expectations. Students should be encouraged to choose live, topical issues, as this supports motivation. Professors are advised to require the use of primary sources such as EU policy documents or official data, ensuring factual precision and policy literacy.
- Offering a short workshop or tutorial on how to structure executive summaries and recommendations can significantly improve outcomes and students’ confidence.
- Combining the brief with debate elements; linking it to DEBUE’s *Debating Europe* or *Scenario-Building* exercise can be useful to reinforce the integration of research, argumentation, and communication/writing skills.
- Make assessments focus not only on the finished product but also on the process: the logic of analysis, the clarity of argument, and the feasibility of recommendations. Ending with a reflective discussion on what the exercise revealed about policymaking, communication, and the relationship between research and practice.

The DEBUE Podcast Series: Co-Creating Europe in Sound

Among the most creative outputs of DEBUE was the Podcast Series, produced with Civitas on Air at Warsaw’s palace of culture.⁷ Podcasts literally transformed the classroom into a recording studio and students into co-creators. The series embodied DEBUE’s commitment to debate and dialogue by asking students not only to study European integration but also to communicate it to a wider audience. Through research, collaborative scripting, production and editing, participants learned how to actively shape interesting ideas, stories and policy developments into sound.

Purpose and Pedagogical Value

Podcasting grew out of DEBUE’s high-impact teaching approach and provided an innovative way to strengthen research, digital literacy, and teamwork, while at the same time, nurturing creativity and critical thinking. The podcast format demanded precision and logical thinking, since students had to make complex topics understandable and relevant, but without undermining intellectual substance, nuance and topicality. You will need a full semester **(25-30 hours of class time) to do two podcasts from start to finish.**

Podcasts advanced DEBUE’s preference for co-creation, namely the idea that meaningful learning emerges when students and teachers share responsibility for producing and interpreting knowledge. Consequently, each stage of the process, from brainstorming to broadcasting and editing was collaborative. Students proposed topics, staff advised on framing and accuracy, and technical mentors from Civitas on Air supported studio-work. This mode of working also helped to ‘flatten traditional

⁷ <https://civitas.edu.pl/en/our-university/news/podcasts-created-as-a-part-of-the-debue-project>

hierarchies’ and gave students a genuine and authentic sense of owning their work. As one student podcaster from Turkey remarked, ‘I felt that my research and views had an audience beyond the classroom’.

Episodes were produced under the joint label of Civitas on Air and DEBUE. Each focused on a clear theme with contemporary relevance to DEBUE’s core themes of democracy, identity, enlargement, and the EU’s global role. Amongst the most popular were those on EU enlargement and the Eurovision Song Contest. Each podcast mixed academic analysis with narrative storytelling, and sharing of viewpoints.⁸

How the Podcasts Were Made: Step-by-Step Process

The production of each episode followed a structured yet flexible path which emphasised collective creativity: - .

1. **Brainstorming topics.** Each cycle began with an open workshop where students proposed ideas drawn from current EU debates, recent lectures, and their own interests. Using collaborative boards, ideas were grouped into clusters such as identity, security, or democracy.
2. **Defining core questions.** Once a theme was chosen, the team identified guiding questions to ensure coherence and clarity.
3. **Scanning the landscape.** Students conducted a short competitor analysis, listening to podcasts by EU institutions, think tanks, and media outlets. They noted tone, length, and gaps in coverage, deciding how their own approach would differ and hopefully innovate.
4. **Choosing a style.** Students select a format — host + guest interview, moderated discussion, or multi-voice storytelling. They set duration (usually 25–30 minutes) and tone. Students decided on titles, introductions, and closing phrases that would make the podcast clearly part of DEBUE.
5. **Research.** Every team compiled a research dossier of primary sources stored on Teams: EU press releases, policy documents, speeches, and data. Extensive discussion is needed at this stage, so allow at least ten hours.
6. **Script.** Students write concise, conversational scripts: short sentences, one idea per line, transitions that guided listeners smoothly. Openings used vivid hooks or questions; conclusions offered 2–3 key takeaways. Drafts were read aloud and edited for rhythm and clarity.
8. **Assigning roles.** Each participant took on specific responsibilities, and a team leader was assigned to each podcast. Constant contact with the professor is essential.
9. **Recording and editing.** Sessions were recorded in the Civitas on Air studio or remotely via Zoom, using separate tracks and basic audio-editing software. Some students got involved in the editing process to ensure quality and accuracy.

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zjqDlpEsSWA>
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RpJw4SsDDSk>
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H86EN2-5p28> https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=LQgt_c8lts
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QB3xiw8ZbLQ>

11. Publishing and promoting. Final episodes were uploaded to the Civitas on Air platform / YouTube, the university website, and Spotify.

12. Reflecting and archiving. Each team completed a short debrief: what worked, what could improve, and what insights were gained. These short reflections compiled by willing students became part of the DEBUE learning portfolio and informed subsequent episodes – see ANNEXE.

Annexes

ANNEXE 1. Kick-off activity

Discovering Your Learning Methodology and Baseline EU Knowledge

Purpose

This short activity helps you understand your personal learning style and study preferences, while also assessing your starting level of knowledge about the European Union and European integration.

Part 1 – Kick-off Quiz: How Much Do You Know About the EU?

Answer individually. There are no grades—this is to see what you already know!

1. How many member states are currently in the European Union?
2. Which institution proposes new EU legislation?
3. What is the difference between the European Council and the Council of the EU?
4. Name two current EU candidate states.
5. What are the Copenhagen Criteria?
6. Which treaty introduced the concept of European citizenship?
7. True or False: The European Parliament can dismiss the European Commission.
8. What does 'European integration' mean to you personally?

Part 2 – Learning Style Reflection

Circle or mark your preferred answers. Be honest—there are no right or wrong answers!

When I'm learning something new, I prefer to: (a) watch or visualise it (b) read about it (c) discuss it (d) try it out

When I prepare for exams or essays, I usually: (a) make mind maps (b) highlight texts (c) work in groups (d) rehearse or apply concepts

I remember information best when I: (a) see images (b) hear explanations (c) write or talk it through (d) do something with it

Part 3 – Your Personal Learning Methodology

In about 150 words, describe your personal learning approach. Include your strengths, challenges, and how you plan to study effectively in this course on the European Union.

Tutor Guide: How Do You Learn – and What Do You Know?

This guide supports the delivery of the student handout exercise. It outlines learning outcomes, suggested timing, and facilitation tips.

Learning Outcomes

Students identify their dominant learning style(s) and reflect on their study habits.

Students produce a short 'personal learning methodology statement.'

Students assess their baseline knowledge of the EU and European integration.

Tutor gains insight into student backgrounds and expectations for the course.

Timing and Structure (Approx. 45–60 minutes)

Part 1 – EU Kick-off Quiz: 10–15 minutes

Part 2 – Learning Style Reflection: 15 minutes

Part 3 – Small Group Discussion: 10 minutes

Part 4 – Personal Learning Methodology Statement: 10–15 minutes

Facilitation Tips

- Use a light, engaging tone during the quiz to encourage participation and curiosity.
- Highlight patterns from quiz answers to introduce course themes on the EU and integration.
- Emphasise that learning styles are flexible and can change; students often use multiple modes.
- Encourage peer exchange as students can learn effective study habits from each other.
- Collect or review students' methodology statements to tailor teaching approaches if needs be.

ANNEXE 2. Student feedback and reflection from DEBUE podcasts

First feedback report (Podcast #1)

When we first learned that we'd be making podcasts as part of our class reactions were mixed. Some people were excited, others hesitant or sceptical. But once the project got underway we gradually saw that it fitted perfectly with what DEBUE was trying to do about raising voices across Europe.

We were asked to choose topics, research them, write speeches, host discussions, and edit episodes. It was ambitious and quite time demanding.

In our group participation levels varied. A few were enthusiastic immediately, but other students stayed quiet or unsure of what they could contribute. Dr Longhurst played a big role in motivation, encouraging everyone to find a task that suited their interests. Her emphasis on team spirit helped turn a group of individuals into a functioning podcast team. Gradually, energy built up and quieter students got involved once they saw that their ideas were being taken seriously.

We started by brainstorming topics based on current EU debates. We then wrote down questions to frame the podcast. EU sources were mostly used. We thought accuracy mattered more than our opinions, at least at the beginning. We also listened to existing podcasts by EU institutions and media outlets to see how we could make ours youthful and fun.

We did script writing and recording. Writing was much harder than writing essays. We had to simplify our language and sound natural. The studio felt intimidating at first, but after a few sessions it became a space of genuine collaboration and mistakes were part of the fun.

After each episode, we held a short debrief on what worked and what we could improve. By the end, the project changed the way we saw both the EU and ourselves. The podcast showed that when everyone has a voice and when professors treat students as partners and co-responsibles creativity an emerge. Doing the podcast made we realise that the EU is not boring.

Second feedback report (podcasts, 3 and 4)

When we began the podcasts, most of us were unsure what to expect. None of us were native English speakers so recording and publishing our voices was unsettling. We worried about how we would sound to others. But the podcast became a rewarding experiences and built our confidence.

Speaking English for a real audience pushed us to listen to one another, correct mistakes together, and focus on meaning rather than perfection. We realised that podcasting was about connection. Every recording session was a small act of international cooperation bringing together students from different countries, accents, and perspectives. Preparing for a podcast requires lots of research. More than we realised, so more help from the professor was needed.

Hearing our voices on the final podcasts reminded us that our student work could reach outside the classroom. If we could change something next time, we would start preparing earlier and spend more time experimenting with different styles and sound effects to make the podcasts more professional.